

Students' character based on gender, grade, and school: religious, nationalism, integrity, independent and cooperative

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to describe students' character value and reveal the relationship of character values in elementary school children based on gender, grade and type of the school. The character values analyzed include religion, nationalism, integrity, independence, and cooperative values. This research was a quantitative method with a cross-sectional design by explaining and analyzing the results using Jeffrey's amazing statistics program (JASP) software and students' character values was categorized and described according to the aspect, gender, grade, and type of the school. Character of elementary school children (CESC) questionnaire was used as an instrument in this study. CESC have very good internal consistency (0.80 to 0.87) and have suitability construct model. The respondent of this study was 862 students obtained through the stratified random sampling randomly technique in elementary school at Yogyakarta Province. The result of this study confirmed that the students' character value is a high level. The lowest aspect is integrity (2.40), while the highest aspect is religious (3.16). There is a relationship between the character values: religion, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative values. It indicates that policymakers or teachers should improve students' character value by training or applying a learning model that focuses explicitly on students' character.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, an appropriate breakthrough is needed, namely the design and educational model that can face the challenges of the 21st century. The demands of the 21st century require graduates who have skills such as creative thinking, problem solving and communication, and character. In the 21st century, character is a very important component of education. Education is seen as an important component for every individual to gain character strength so that he can adapt to developments in the 21st century and contribute to global society [1]. The inculcation of character values plays a very important role in developing one's attitudes and behavior in daily life which is full of challenges. Character

education will form a positive character in the individual [2]. Character education starts from the “inside” in humans (learners) [3]. The importance of character education in order to encourage students to practice speaking respectfully to others, volunteering, being a responsible citizen, and building decision-making and problem-solving skills [4]. Character education need to implement in all level education to avoid character crises. Character crises often occur due to problematic behaviors including delinquency, antisocial tendencies, and risky behavior [5]. Character education is expected to avoid or overcome a character crisis. There are ten signs of the times that must be avoided: theft, violence and vandalism, fraud, disrespect for authority figures, bigotry, use of bad language and words, cruelty towards peers, sexual harassment, self-destructive behavior, and selfishness and decreased responsibility. To avoid these threats, character strength is needed [6].

Character is the mental and moral qualities distinctive to an individual that is built since childhood and continues to grow. The development and formation of character is the ultimate goal of children's education in schools. Children's education through the teaching process and the availability of facilities helps children in building their character. Many character values are integrated into each subject [7]. The values of character education in children such as caring, honesty, justice, responsibility, and respect for oneself and others [8]. Character values such as integrity, courage, justice, and forgiveness, but also other positive values such as curiosity, social intelligence, teamwork, and humor [9]. Good character is the values of kindness, such as honesty, justice, courage, and compassion [10]. Eight positive values that are emphasized are obedience, religious respect, cheerfulness, kindness, thrift, hopeful future hope, trust, and helping [11]. There are six pillars of very important character values, namely trust, respect, responsibility, fairness, caring, citizenship, honesty, integrity, reliability, and loyalty [12]. Many character values are references to be instilled in children and based on the stage of development of elementary school-age children, religious values, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative need to be known. Elementary school children have been considered a sensitive period for behavioral adjustment [13]. There are some skills in 21st century according to foundation literacies (literacy, numeracy, and information & communication technology (ICT)), competencies (critical thinking, creativity, communication, and collaboration), and character qualities [14]. Research on character values in elementary school children has attracted attention in recent years. However, very few studies have examined the relationship between character values in elementary school children that shape character strength in children.

The problem in this study is that the relationship or linkage of character values in elementary school students has not been investigated. The elements that play a role and are responsible for character education in schools are school principals, teachers, staff employees, students, as well as families and community members [10]. the formation of student character is influenced by the school environment. The development and formation of the character of each child is inseparable from external and internal factors [4]. The process of implementing character education in elementary schools has long been implemented and has formed a unique character strength in elementary school children. The unique character of students has not been revealed by many researchers. This character will have an impact on students' abilities to face the development of the 21st century.

There have been many articles published in reputable journals related to the character. For example, many research measures the character strength of adolescents, but none of these studies reveal the relationship between character values in elementary school children [15]–[17]. So that the focus of this research is to reveal the relationship of character values in elementary school children with the network analysis method. Network analysis is very important and effective in the decision-making process about the relationship between character values. Information on each unique character relationships that elementary school children have during the educational process at school is obtained. So that it becomes the basis for teachers and schools in implementing character education in an integrated manner.

The results of the document analysis of the research on character education for primary school students showed several problem points. One of the main problems is that there is no valid, effective, and proven instrument to measure the character education of primary school students. There has been no research that designs test instruments at the elementary school level. This research produces an instrument that is proven to be valid and accountable for measuring the character education of elementary school students. This instrument was analyzed using Jeffrey's amazing statistics program (JASP) which shows the value of internal consistency, validity, chi square, root and mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) as a form of item response theory (IRT). The instrument can even measure the relationship between the measured aspects including religious, nationalism, integrity, independent and cooperative values. Thus, the research question of this study was formulated as:

- i) What is the quality of the character education test instrument for elementary school students to measure aspects of religious, nationalism, integrity, independent and cooperative values?
- ii) What is the level of character of elementary school students based on differences in gender, grade, and type of the school?

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This type of research is quantitative with survey type. The type of survey chosen, namely the student/school survey aims to determine the efficiency and effectiveness of character education, so that values or character are formed in elementary school children. In survey research, collecting information from a group of respondents by asking several survey questions, so this research produces data in the form of numbers which are the results of filling out questionnaires measuring the character of elementary school children (CESC).

The research sites are in Indonesia, Central Java Province, especially in the areas of Sleman, Gunung Kidul, Kulon Progo, Bantul, and Yogyakarta. The research sample came from 862 children in grades 4th-6th of elementary school with 408 male students and 454 female students. This study has been granted ethical approval by the Alma Ata University. Prior to data collection, written informed consent was obtained from all participants. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines established by the Research and Community Service Institute or LPPM Alma Ata University. The sampling technique to be used is probability sampling, specifically simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is a commonly employed sampling technique in quantitative research involving survey instruments. It is generally considered suitable for populations that are both homogeneous and uniformly distributed. This method ensures that every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected, making the selection process entirely random [18].

CESC questionnaire was used to measure students' character in the elementary school. CESC is a Likert scale with tiered choices, namely never, never, sometimes, and always. If a positive statement is responded to by elementary school children, then it is never (1), never (2), sometimes (3), and always (4). Meanwhile, if the negative statement is responded to by elementary school children, it is never (4), never (3), sometimes (2), and always (1). Giving the questionnaire via the Google Form link. The complete description of the questionnaire for measuring the character of school children and structure of CESC questionnaire are shown in Table 1. Data analysis was performed using quantitative descriptive methods. Students' character value was described in several aspects including the domain of character values, gender, grade, and type of the school. To determine the level of students' character value, the rubric of the given questionnaire was grouped as seen in Table 2.

Table 1. The structure of the CESC questionnaire

The aspect of character value	Indicator	No questionnaire	
		Positive	Negative
Religious	Carry out God's commands (individual relationship with God vertically)	R1, R3	R2
	Carrying out God's commands (relationships between humans)	R4, R5, R6, R7, R8	
	Carrying out God's commands (Individual's relationship with the environment)	R9, R10,	R11
Nationalism	Have a sense of pride in their own nation's culture	N1, N2, N3	
	Accepting religious/cultural/ethnic/nation/racial diversity	N4,	N5
	Prioritizing common interests	N6, N9	N7, N8
Integrity	Responsible as a school citizen	I1, I2	
	Respect the dignity of individuals, especially persons with disabilities	I4	I3, I5
	Honest/trustworthy in word and deed	I8	I6, I7
Independent	Behavior does not depend on others	M1, M2	M29
	Responsible for every activity	M3, M4	M5
	Act and act unyielding	M7, M8	M6
Cooperative	The spirit of cooperation in solving problems	G1, G2	
	Likes to help friends in need	G3, G4	G5
	Deliberation in consensus	G6	G7, G8

Table 2. Level of students' character value

Range	Level
0-0.49	Very low
0.50-1.49	Low
1.50-2.49	Average
2.50-3.49	High
3.50-4.00	Very high

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Instrument quality

Instrument quality measurement data were analyzed using structural equation modeling involving model construction. Data analysis followed the network analysis procedure to investigate the relationship or

relationship of character values that were formed and developed in elementary school children. In addition, network analysis is able to explore the pattern of complex relationships between character values in different phenomena. The network structure consists of nodes and edges. Here, the nodes represent the objects to be analyzed, while the edges represent the relationships between these objects. The software used is JASP 0.14.1.0. JASP software can generate a variety of network shapes that are visualized, centrality, clustering plots, and centrality, clustering, and weighting matrix tables. Network analysis is a method used to model the interaction between many variables to estimate the relationship between all variables. Network analysis involves the relationship between variables without assuming the existence of certain latent constructs that can be visualized by graphical models. The network graph obtained from JASP is a graph of R packets [19]. Network analysis implemented in JASP allows any user to examine the relationships between discrete entities in a data set based on network theory.

Figure 1 showed the results of the internal consistency calculation for the CESC questionnaire which ranged from 0.80 to 0.87 (very good). The instrument is said to be good if the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is above 0.7 [20]. While all items of the questionnaire instrument statement are in the valid category. The results of proving the suitability of the character value construct model with empirical data indicate a fit construct model. These results are reinforced by the value of chi-square=125.25, p-value=0.0218, goodness of fit index (GFI)=0.92, RMSEA=0.052, non-normed fit index (NNFI)=0.99, parsimony normed fit index (PNFI)=0.87, comparative fit index (CFI)=0.99, and incremental fit index (IFI)=0.99 which met the fit limit. The criteria used through estimation of the factor weight coefficient it is known that each character value has a factor weight >0.50 or it can be stated that all items on religious values have sufficient validity [21].

Figure 1. The result of proving the character value construct

3.2. Students' character values based on the indicator

This section provides an analysis of students' character values across five domains: religious, nationalistic, integrity, independent, and cooperative. Table 3 presents a detailed breakdown of these values. In the religious domain, students demonstrated the highest level of commitment to proper waste disposal (item 9), while the lowest was regarding avoiding distractions during learning (item 11). For nationalism, students exhibited strong inclusivity (item 15) and a low tolerance for discriminatory behavior (item 16). Regarding integrity, students consistently adhered to school uniform regulations (item 21) but showed a lack of empathy towards those with physical disabilities (item 23). In terms of independence, students were diligent in completing assignments (item 32) but struggled with academic honesty (item 34). Finally, in the cooperative domain, students actively participated in group discussions (item 43) and displayed a low tendency to ridicule peers' opinions (item 44). Overall, the students exhibited a commendable level of character values, demonstrating a strong foundation in various aspects of ethical behavior.

There are 45 questionnaires that measure students' character values. This questionnaire was developed from 15 indicators of student character values in Table 4. Based on Table 4, the highest indicator is the integrity aspect, where the highest average score obtained reached 3.80 (very high) for "responsible as a school citizen". Even though it obtained the highest average score, the integrity aspect also showed the lowest average score. This is shown by the indicator "respect the dignity of individuals, especially persons

with disabilities” which received a score of 1.78 in the moderate category. Overall, the students' character values are in the good or high category.

Table 3. The result of students' character value based on aspect

Aspect	Mean	SD	Description
Religious	3.16	1.11	High
Nationalist	2.75	1.27	High
Integrity	2.40	1.20	Moderate
Independent	2.68	1.20	High
Cooperative	2.49	1.27	Moderate
Overall	2.69	1.27	High

Table 4. The result of students' character value based on indicators

Aspect	Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
Religious	Carry out God's commands (individual relationship with God vertically)	3.16	1.11	High
	Carrying out God's commands (relationships between humans)	2.75	1.27	High
Nationalism	Carrying out God's commands (Individual's relationship with the environment)	2.40	1.20	Moderate
	Have a sense of pride in their own nation's culture	3.19	0.95	High
	Accepting religious/cultural/ethnic/nation/racial diversity	2.48	1.46	Moderate
Integrity	Prioritizing common interests	2.55	1.22	High
	Responsible as a school citizen	3.80	0.55	Very high
	Respect the dignity of individuals, especially persons with disabilities	1.78	1.15	Moderate
Independent	Honest/trustworthy in word and deed	2.07	1.30	Moderate
	Behavior does not depend on others	2.54	1.02	High
	Responsible for every activity	2.96	1.35	High
Cooperative	Act and act unyielding	2.53	1.15	High
	The spirit of cooperation in solving problems	3.23	0.90	High
	Likes to help friends in need	2.52	1.17	High
	Deliberation in consensus	1.96	1.33	Moderate

3.3. Students' character values based on the gender

This section presents a gender-based analysis of students' character values, as detailed in Table 5. In the religious domain, both male and female students demonstrated a strong commitment to practicing their faith (item 4). However, both genders struggled with maintaining focus during religious activities (item 11), with females showing slightly lower scores. Regarding nationalism, both genders exhibited a high level of inclusivity (item 15). Nevertheless, both groups displayed intolerance towards individuals from different backgrounds (item 16), with males showing a slightly lower level of tolerance. In terms of integrity, both genders consistently adhered to school rules and regulations (item 21) but struggled with empathy towards individuals with disabilities (item 23), with males showing slightly lower empathy. For independence, male students excelled in completing assignments (item 32), while female students demonstrated strong self-reliance (item 33). Both genders faced challenges with academic honesty (item 34), with males exhibiting lower levels of integrity in this area. In the cooperative domain, both genders actively participated in group discussions (item 43) and displayed low tolerance for disrespectful behavior towards peers (item 44), with females showing slightly higher levels of cooperation. Overall, female students demonstrated slightly higher levels of character values than male students, with both groups exhibiting high levels of character development. To further obtaining better understanding, the multivariate analysis of variance or MANOVA test was conducted to prove whether there were significant differences in students' character value based on gender. There are no significant differences in integrity and independent aspect with sig value are >0.05 but there is a significant difference in religious, nationalism and cooperative aspect where sig value is <0.05 . Table 6 shows the analysis of MANOVA test.

Table 5. The result of students' character value based on gender

Aspect	Male			Female		
	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
Religious	3.08	1.13	High	3.19	1.13	High
Nationalism	2.44	1.24	Average	2.78	1.29	High
Integrity	2.39	1.35	Average	2.40	1.39	Average
Independent	2.66	1.18	High	2.69	1.23	High
Cooperative	2.43	1.23	Average	2.54	1.31	High
Overall	2.60	1.23	High	2.72	1.27	High

Table 6. MANOVA test based on gender

Source	Dependent variable	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Gender	Religious	2.559	1	2.559	24.515	0.000
	Nationalism	0.826	1	0.826	9.357	0.002
	Integrity	0.058	1	0.058	0.665	0.415
	Independent	0.225	1	0.225	2.350	0.126
	Cooperative	2.680	1	2.680	23.681	0.000

3.4. Students' character values based on the grade

This section provides a grade-level analysis of students' character values, as detailed in Table 7. Across all grades, students demonstrated a strong commitment to religious practices and beliefs, as evidenced by the high scores for item 9. However, all grades struggled with maintaining focus during religious activities, as indicated by the low scores for item 11. All grades exhibited strong nationalistic sentiments, particularly in terms of inclusivity and tolerance (item 15). However, there was a noticeable lack of understanding or appreciation for diverse cultures and backgrounds, as reflected in the low scores for item 10. Students in all grades demonstrated a high level of integrity, particularly in adhering to school rules and regulations (item 21). However, they struggled with empathy and compassion for individuals with disabilities, as indicated by the low scores for item 23. Grades 4th and 5th excelled in completing assignments independently (item 32), while grade 6th demonstrated strong self-reliance (item 33). However, all grades faced challenges with academic honesty, as evidenced by the low scores for item 34. All grades actively participated in group discussions and exhibited positive cooperative behaviors (item 43). However, they struggled with respecting diverse opinions and avoiding disrespectful behavior, as indicated by the low scores for items 44 and 45. The overall character education scores for all grades were high, indicating a strong foundation in character values. However, there is room for improvement in specific areas, such as focus during religious activities, understanding of diverse cultures, empathy for individuals with disabilities, and respectful behavior in group settings.

Table 7. The result of students' character value based on grade

Aspect	Grade four(4th)			Grade five (5th)			Grade six (6th)		
	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
Religious	3.13	1.13	High	3.15	1.13	High	3.11	1.14	High
Nationalism	2.73	1.09	High	2.76	1.07	High	2.74	1.05	High
Integrity	2.38	1.36	Average	2.41	1.38	Average	2.38	1.37	Average
Independent	2.66	1.19	High	2.70	1.20	High	2.66	1.37	High
Cooperative	2.45	1.06	Average	2.51	1.11	High	2.50	1.11	High
Overall	2.67	1.26	High	2.71	1.27	High	2.67	1.27	High

To further obtaining better understanding, the multivariate analysis of variance or MANOVA test was conducted to prove whether there were significant differences in students' character value based on grade. There are no significant differences in religious, nationalism, integrity and independent aspect with sig value are >0.05 but there is a significant difference in cooperative aspect where sig value is $0.026 < 0.05$. Table 8 shows the analysis of MANOVA test.

Table 8. MANOVA test based on grade

Source	Dependent variable	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Observed power
Grade	Religious	2	0.147	1.373	0.254	0.296
	Nationalism	2	0.117	1.315	0.269	0.285
	Integrity	2	0.156	1.795	0.167	0.376
	Independent	2	0.250	2.610	0.074	0.521
	Cooperative	2	0.421	3.646	0.026	0.673

3.5. Students' character values based on the type of the school

This section provides a comparison of students' character values based on the type of school: public and private, as outlined in Table 9. Both public and private school students demonstrated a strong commitment to religious practices and beliefs, as evidenced by the high scores for item 9. However, both groups struggled with maintaining focus during religious activities, as indicated by the low scores for item 11. Both public and private school students exhibited strong nationalistic sentiments, particularly in terms of inclusivity and tolerance (item 15). However, there was a noticeable lack of understanding or

appreciation for diverse cultures and backgrounds, as reflected in the low scores for item 16. Students in both public and private schools demonstrated a high level of integrity, particularly in adhering to school rules and regulations (item 21). However, both groups struggled with empathy and compassion for individuals with disabilities, as indicated by the low scores for item 23. Both public and private school students demonstrated strong independent learning skills, with high scores for items 32 and 33. However, both groups faced challenges with academic honesty, as evidenced by the low scores for item 34. Both public and private school students actively participated in group discussions and exhibited positive cooperative behaviors (item 43). However, both groups struggled with respecting diverse opinions and avoiding disrespectful behavior, as indicated by the low scores for items 44 and 45. While both public and private school students exhibited high levels of character development, private school students demonstrated slightly higher scores overall. This suggests that private schools may have a slightly stronger emphasis on character education or provide a more conducive environment for character development. However, it's important to note that both groups have areas for improvement, particularly in the areas of focus during religious activities, understanding of diverse cultures, empathy, and respectful behavior.

Table 9. The result of students' character value based on type of the school

Aspect	Public school			Private school		
	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
Religious	3.13	1.14	High	3.11	1.16	High
Nationalism	2.76	1.09	High	2.79	1.12	High
Integrity	2.42	1.40	Average	2.09	1.25	Average
Independent	2.68	1.40	High	2.77	1.25	High
Cooperative	2.49	1.09	Average	2.41	1.16	Average
Overall	2.60	1.23	High	2.63	1.27	High

To further obtaining better understanding, the MANOVA test was conducted to prove whether there were significant differences in students' character value based on type of the school. There are no significant differences in religious, nationalism, independent and cooperative aspect with sig value are >0.05 but there is a significant difference in integrity aspect where sig value is $0.026 < 0.05$. Table 10 shows the analysis of MANOVA test.

Table 10. MANOVA test based on type of the school

Source	Dependent variable	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Observed power
Type school	Religious	1	0.035	0.330	0.566	0.088
	Nationalism	1	0.207	2.354	0.125	0.335
	Integrity	1	1.414	16.615	0.000	0.983
	Independence	1	0.086	0.895	0.344	0.157
	Cooperative	1	0.068	0.586	0.444	0.119

3.6. The relationship of character values

The relationship of character values that are formed and developed in elementary school children, namely religious, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative values during the character education process can be identified through network analysis. Network analysis is carried out to describe the relationship or relationship between the values of the characters that are formed. The results of the analysis are shown in Figure 2. Degree shows that there is a node with a higher degree, so it has a higher centrality. Betweenness shows the number of paths between two nodes that pass through a certain node can be interpreted as centrality between nodes. Closeness shows the length of the path from one node to another node in the network, so it is considered the centrality of the proximity of the node.

Figure 2 shows that the character values of elementary school children that are formed and developed during the character education process have values between kinship, closeness, degree, and expected influence. The statement items of religious character values, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative have a value betweenness of -1 to 3. The items of statements of religious character values, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative have a closeness value of -3 to 2. The statement items of religious character values, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative have a value of degree -2.5 to 2.5. The statement items of religious, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative values have an expected influence value of -3 to 2. Thus, the character values formed in elementary school children have a positive relationship, closeness, degree, and expectation of influence.

Table 11. Centrality measures per variable

Variable	Network			
	Betweenness	Closeness	Strength	Expected influence
R1	-0.732	-0.209	0.157	0.547
R2	-1.095	-1.219	-1.683	-2.819
R3	-0.864	-1.087	-1.286	-0.663
R4	-0.005	0.881	0.492	-0.043
R5	-1.095	-0.976	-0.964	-0.016
R6	0.556	0.967	0.475	1.376
R7	-0.137	0.348	-0.260	0.530
R8	0.226	0.939	1.025	1.309
R9	0.721	1.138	0.437	-0.662
R10	-0.996	-.610	-1.316	-0.696
R11	0.358	-.683	-0.156	0.231
R12	-0.401	.330	0.122	0.854
N1	-1.095	-2.877	-2.347	-1.352
N2	1.811	1.153	1.022	-0.133
N3	2.009	1.145	1.048	1.416
N4	-0.104	0.489	0.480	-0.041
N5	0.886	1.141	0.703	1.164
N6	0.886	-0.031	0.809	0.654
N7	0.226	0.300	0.014	-1.209
N8	-0.633	0.018	0.287	0.603
I1	-0.368	-0.311	-0.374	-1.079
I2	-0.269	-0.024	0.764	0.934
I3	3.396	1.836	2.249	1.212
I4	-0.864	-1.271	-1.668	-0.801
I5	-1.095	0.203	-1.244	-0.432
I6	0.292	0.239	0.352	0.959
I7	-1.095	-1.364	-1.275	-0.861
I8	-1.029	-0.390	0.021	0.937
M1	-0.930	-1.717	-1.463	-1.999
M2	-1.095	-1.322	-1.184	-0.597
M3	-0.732	-0.768	-0.914	-0.931
M4	0.919	1.451	1.402	0.102
M5	1.250	1.109	1.337	1.822
M6	1.217	0.855	0.585	0.299
M7	-0.963	-0.446	-0.447	-0.767
M8	-0.302	-0.178	-0.185	0.098
M9	0.127	-0.599	0.701	-0.171
G1	1.118	0.001	1.260	1.845
G2	-0.699	-0.243	-0.474	-0.025
G3	-0.401	-0.465	-0.512	-0.362
G4	-0.897	-1.183	-0.365	-0.115
G5	-0.038	0.585	-0.314	-1.090
G6	0.655	1.449	0.631	0.858
G7	0.424	0.141	1.109	-0.085
G8	0.853	1.249	0.948	-0.803

Figure 3. The network of character values, religious, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative

The relationship of character values in elementary school children is inseparable from the value of religious character. Religiosity relates to one's personal relationship with God [22]. The system of values and beliefs that a child believes will be organized that serve as a moral and social guide. The most important sign for a child to be religious properly is to be able to practice the teachings of the religion he adheres to in everyday life. Meanwhile, moral competence and spirituality affect the development of children's behavior [23]. In addition, there are findings that show a link between behavior such as moral competence and spirituality [24]. Spirituality is an important source of resilience, an asset in dealing with negative life experiences, and can help adolescents overcome life's difficulties and problems in an adaptive way [25]. The religious value shown by elementary school students is not only limited to moral knowing and moral feeling but is already a habitual moral action (habit).

Children who have religious character values will have the character values of nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative. All these character values will be seen during social interactions. It is important to promote positive behavior or attitudes towards children and facilitate social interactions and traditional relationships between children. Every child at a certain age has a unique characteristic in the development of his character and continues to develop towards a more complex direction in adolescence. Unique characters will emerge from each child [26]. Religiosity and nationalism are important components of the collective mind or collective consciousness, namely the unifying force in society and communities [27]. The results of the study show that the cooperative shown by elementary school children is the spirit of cooperation in solving problems. This finding is in line with previous research that children who develop more empathy tend to enjoy friendship with their peers and solve problems in cooperation [28]. The independent of elementary school children shows that they are able to be responsible in every activity.

The existence of a relationship between the values of elementary school characters, namely religious, nationalism, integrity, independent, and cooperative is the government's foothold in strengthening integrated character education for elementary school children. These character values must be the focus of teachers in inculcating character values in elementary schools either on a micro or macro basis, so that elementary school children have character strength. The development and formation of a child's character is influenced by many factors [29]. Long-lasting behavior patterns that can be generalized into personality characteristics [30]. Habits and examples that have been introduced and shown by the teacher to their students, cause students to follow what the teacher sees (moral action). The strength of character values possessed by children will be the basis for social interaction in the school, community, and family environment. In addition, it can be used in adapting to the times in the 21st century. Several studies mention the contribution of character strength to student success [31]–[33]. Students in the Central Java Province, especially in the areas of Sleman, Gunung Kidul, Kulon Progo, Bantul, and Yogyakarta have good character qualities that can be used as a guide in interacting with anyone and academic improvement. The Business and Industry Advisory Committee to the OECD Survey reveals that in this complex world, entrepreneurs are increasingly aware of the importance of character quality [34]. Having good character qualities makes elementary school children able to face the developments of the 21st century. There are at least three categories of skills needed, namely literacy, competence, and quality of character [14].

4. CONCLUSION

The research findings show that there is a close relationship or connection between the values of religious character, nationalism, integrity, independence and cooperative. Thus, the character values formed in elementary school children have a positive relationship, closeness, degree and expectation of influence. Religious character values have an impact on increasing other character values, so that the influence of these four-character values must be considered. These character values play a dominant role in shaping the daily behavior of elementary school children. Unique character values support the birth of elementary school children who are ready to face 21st century skills. Elementary school children will seek information, not be given information, because the 21st century is the information age. The character quality of each child is the hallmark of a superior generation. Gender differences in the relationship between character values in elementary school children should be investigated in future research.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest. This research was conducted in an objective and unbiased manner. There are no financial, personal, or professional relationships that could have influenced the research, its findings, or its conclusions. All authors have contributed equally to this work, and there are no competing interests that might compromise the integrity of this study.

INFORMED CONSENT

The protection of privacy is a legal right that must not be breached without individual informed consent. In cases where the identification of personal information is necessary for scientific reasons, authors should obtain full documentation of informed consent, including written permission from the patient prior to inclusion in the study. Incorporate the following (or a similar) statement: We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The research related to human use has been complied with all the relevant national regulations and institutional policies in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration and has been approved by the authors' institutional review board or equivalent committee.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [RP], upon reasonable request.

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